

Electricity Sector in Suriname – pathways to promote renewable energy insertion

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Presentation Outline

- Context, challenges & Research Question
- Suriname Reference Energy System
- Scenarios
- Results
- **Conclusions, Policy insights, & Future Work**

Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

- Suriname has 600 thousand inhabitants with 70% living in the Capital city of Paramaribo and surroundings.
- The total installed capacity is 510 MW with 37% from hydropower.
- The challenge is to elaborate policies to stimulate entrepreneurs to invest in biomass, wind, solar and hydro.
- What is the optimal mix of renewable energy and what is cost efficient strategy to achieve the 47% renewable target by 2027;

Source : Eenergy Authority Suriname

Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

 ISOLATED GRIDS
GRID A,B,C

 WIND

 SOLAR

 BIO

 SMALL HYFRO

Source : Energy Authority Suriname

Technologies GRID 1 (EPAR)

	Existing technologies		Installed capacity
PWRHFO101	EBS DPP 1	EPAR	39.5 MW
PWRHFO102	EBS DPP 2	EPAR	126.0 MW
PWRHFO103	Staatsolie SPCS thermal	EPAR	96.0 MW
PWRHYD101	Staatsolie SPCS Hydro	EPAR	189.0 MW
PWRTRN101	Transmission Lines	EPAR	
PWRDIST101	Distribution Lines	EPAR	

	Planned technologies		Projected capacity
PWRHFO104	EBS DPP 3	EPAR	
PWRSOL101	SOLAR PLANT	EPAR	
PWRTRN102	Transmission line Grid 1 to Grid 2 bidirectional 2 modes		
PWRTRN103	Transmission line Grid 1 to Grid 3 bidirectional 3 modes		

Technologies Grid 3 (ENIC) Grid 2 (Albina)

Existing Technologies Nickerie			
PWRHFO201	EBS Nickerie Clara polder	ENIC	22.0 MW
PWRDIST201	EBS Distribution lines	ENIC	

Planned Technologies Nickerie			
PWRSOL201	Solar power plant Nickerie	ENIC	
PWRBIO201	Rice Husk Bio power plant Nickerie	ENIC	
PWRWND201	Wind power plant Nickerie	ENIC	

Existing technologies Albina			
PWRDSL301	Diesel Power Plant Albina	Albina	9.0 MW
PWRDIST301	Distribution lines Albina	Albina	

Planned Technologies Albina			
PWRHYD301	SHP Grankriki	Albina	
PWRTRN301	Transmission line	Albina	

GRID 1 - (EPAR)

GRID 2 – (ENICK)

GRID 3 - ALBINA

National targets

- Suriname has committed during the 41st Special Meeting of COTED (Council for Trade and Economic Development) on a **target of 47% renewable power capacity** and at the same time CO₂ reductions of 36% in the power sector by **2027**.

Scenarios

Using the **OSeMOSYS** Linear Programming Energy System Model and **Flextool** the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
BAU	Business as usual without special policies on renewable insertion	Actual market mechanism will be sufficient to promote the insertion of renewables to attend the 46% target by 2027.
REINS	Renewable insertion in isolated regional grids	Is the best strategy to insert renewables in the isolated grids around the country ?
NGI	National grid integration with renewable insertion	What will be the effect of an national grid integrating for optimal renewable energy penetration ?

Production by Technology Annual

Scenarios Matrix

	None	A to B	B to C	Both
37% Renew 2027	BAU			
47% Renew 2027	Solar Insertion			
57 % Renew 2027				

- **STEP 1 – Check if normal Market mechanism can achieve goal**
- **STEP 2 – Implement a dummy technology to guarantee 47% of renewables using Total Technology Annual Activity Lower Limit**

Solar insertion suggested by the model

Production by technology

Plan of action

- Building an Suriname Starter kit SAND Excell interface from a blank SAND interface v.12 <https://zenodo.org/record/6203284>
- Look for strategies in Sand to interconnect the isolated electrical system
- Constrain selection to implement renewable insertion and interconnection
 - Renewable insertion according to targets using **TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityLowerLimit** for the renewables PWRSQL, PWRWIND and PWRBIO
 - Force minimum flow through networks **TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityLowerLimit PWRTRNA, PWRTRNB, PWRTRNC**